

Theoretical and Philosophical Article

The Philosopher's Stone and Early Affective Factors

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I dedicate this article, with which I conclude my passage in this world, to my teachers, Elon Lages Lima and Ernesto Bruno Cossi.

–R. R. Baldino

December 2024

Porto Alegre, RS, Brazil

Initial Words²

I have avoided shaping this paper into the usual academic format: abstract, keywords, introduction, situation of the problem with references, development and final words. I have written it as it was generated: first, a dream was reported in a discussion list. Then the received stimulus impelled me to examine some consequences of the dipole as the philosophical stone. Then I sought to publish it. The necessary revision showed me some sharp edges that should be smoothed off and the necessity of grounding the implications to teaching in the logic of the signifier, hence the rather long development of the section on early affective cognition factors. Perhaps I can also use this development to argue how the constraint of a paper to the usual academic format may eliminate its novelty, its interdisciplinarity and its critical aftermath.

The Dream

I dreamed that I was talking with stones. I was sitting by a stream with stones piled up on the bank. One of them had called me. I found it. It was that one over there, within reach of my right hand. I picked it up. It was dark, shaped like an ellipsoid about 15 cm in its longest axis. Was it you who called me?! It nodded and told me to look around. My personal things were scattered everywhere. Must be from cleaning my office after I died, I thought. Looking to the left, I saw a stone that looked like a concrete block, with two holes lined with copper. I recognized it. You

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² I am indebted to Alexandre Pais for many interesting remarks on a draft of this paper. To Alexander Moore, I must say: *Tu deviens responsable pour toujours de ce que tu as apprivoisé.*

Received: 9 November 2024 / Revised: 19 December 2024 / Published Online: 23 December 2024

were on my desk... I felt an infinite pity for it, abandoned there as it was. I picked it up. I will take you back, I promised. I pointed to the other stone and explained: it was that one that called me. I felt like I should thank it. At that point, I woke up, very sad for not having had time to rescue it.

It was three in the morning. I got up, stumbling. I emptied the urine bag I am forced to use for what remains of my life. Distractedly, instead of opening the valve on the bag, I uncovered the water bottle, and the cap fell into the toilet. I rescued it and went back to sleep. I dreamed that I was passing by the historical site where I was once hit by a stone thrown by another five-year-old boy during our war games. To the right, the stone wall supporting the neighboring lot had been raised and plastered. They must have done this during the night, I thought; it wasn't like this yesterday... I remembered that the stone would be on the other side of the wall; I had to get there. There's still time to save it, I thought, but I woke up again and began pondering the dream. Now, you say, talking to stones... but that one... poor thing, it made me feel infinite pity... The next day, I told the dream to Tânia (my wife), and then to the speech therapist who visits me twice a week. They found it amusing. The speech therapist³ commented: why precisely the stone that was on your desk?

Days later, the dream appeared during the Maharishi Mahesh Yogi⁴ meditation I've been practicing since 1960, when Doris and Alexandre Cosmelli initiated me, in Porto Alegre. In the depth of the silence achieved through this practice, if done well, one encounters for a few moments what some call the soul, others call God, and still others call the unconscious.

When Tânia came to help me with hydration via the gastric tube, as she does three times a day, I asked her: What is the dream's signifier? She hesitated. It was you who told me, I insisted, ...back in the doctor's office... don't you remember? She was shocked: *I said that?* Yes, when the doctor prescribed Toragesic... You reminded me that this medication hardens the stool, almost like stones...

The scene with the doctor had appeared in the meditation. From deep down, evidence that I could not refuse had emerged. It appears as images of scenes that unfold. *Those stones in the dream were my stool.* I recalled Lacan; facing the poop, the mother says to her son: *it is you but it is not yours* (Lacan, 2004, XXII-3). I must have gone through that, like almost all of us did. We accept the rejection of one part to keep the other and be accepted in society. Even a cat knows how to do that. On this primary rejection, the others are built. *Love your symptom as you love yourself*, said Lacan. My dear stone, I want to pick you up... I love you as I love myself and my tumor. I had found the *philosopher's stone*. When I understood this, a smile came upon me, even while meditating. Each of us is an ambulant and perennial primary rejection, I thought. *The stool goes into the intestines, the ideas go to the head.* The suggestion from the speech therapist occurred to me. Why exactly that stone and why my desk? Two holes lined with copper... are waiting for two axes to pass through... Ah, on my desk lies Hegel's Logic, *Wissenschaft der Logik*. Well then, *Wissenschaft* in German means science, and *Schaft* is 'shaft', in English it means axis. The gaps without axes are my two failed attempts to understand this study book over 30 years ago; hence my sadness. Tânia laughed when I shared this understanding that touched on her psychoanalysis, done many years ago. I added: there are cases where the movement inverts itself, Netanyahu is a case in point. She laughed.

In meditation, it hadn't seemed absurd to consider that this rejection remained invariant when, due to the signifier, the primate became man. This rejection is prior to language; it needs to be said. *Wo es war soll Ich werden*, Freud said (Lacan, 1973, IV-1). *Where this was, the Je must become.* The *Je* had already reached there; but the *Moi* was still missing; Lacan clarified that the *Ich* in Freud is the *Je* in French; blessed is the French language for this difference (Lacan, 1981, XXI-3)! Taking

³ Cecilia Rosso.

⁴ <https://meditacaotranscendental.com.br/>

the *Moi* there is what I am doing now, with considerable reduction of meaning. From the heart of meditation emerged a dipole⁵, a potential for the separation of things that must become affectively opposed. Each of us is that, every living being is that. The tension present in the philosopher's stone separates the ideas from the excrement and elevates the utterance: every man is the whole man, or rather, *there is only one living being in the universe*. The differences come from the literacy along the journey.

On a Special Colleague

Understanding this process bursts into everyday life, where situations occur that are regarded as madness, to a greater or lesser degree. When I was an engineering student, I had a classmate who, in the midst of a normal conversation, would bring his hand to his mouth, widen his eyes, explode into laughter and begin a *pobbb*, which he muffled in a fit of convulsive laughter for about fifteen seconds. We would ask why he was laughing, but he never answered. The situation got complicated when he began doing this during classes, even when sitting in the front row. During a visit by School of Engineering class to a hydroelectric plant in the state, when the resident engineer introduced his family, all dressed up for the occasion, there came the *pobbb*... I believe he saw the formatting that the philosophical dipole had imposed to the bourgeois family; it was clear to him how the interlocutor was using the philosopher's stone. Recalling this scene, I had to be careful not to laugh like him at my family and the things I have done since then. Life can very well end with a *pobbb*... There is nothing more to be understood.

But I took my discovery seriously and told it to Tânia, who indeed found my conclusion funny. I added: this explains that the fundamental dipole guides living organisms since even before language. Contradictions are caused by the fundamental trauma in childhood, and the individual is condemned to cope with their choices as best they can. The symptoms of these contradictions are diseases; cancer is one of them. It is through this wound in my neck that my beloved philosopher's stone emerges. She laughed a bit more. I reflected: yes, a miracle saint performs no miracles at home.

The next day, during the first hydration of the morning, Tânia happily told me about the dream she had had. She was here in our yard watching the tenant who works two days a week for us cover a wall with ornamental stones, common here in the region. Next to him was his brother, who passed away from cirrhosis many years ago. In the dream, she told the tenant: we need to find something for him to do too. When she finished, I reflected: the unconscious wants what it wants; and we burst into laughter. There was no more to say, the book of life was open. After all, we have been together for more than 40 years, we are the Cabralinos. Marrying her was the only right thing I did in my life.

I posted this story on the SBEM⁶ discussion list. The next day I received two comments from colleagues: *it brightened my day*. So that nobody will say I didn't speak of flowers, I replied, I will consider the classroom: *It's you but it's not yours*, the mother says to the son. But... isn't that exactly what the teacher says to the student in the face of a mistake?! With greater or lesser gentleness, of course. You are this that you said and wrote, but the meaning of this is not yours. Students learn to reject that highlighted part of themselves; they learn to consider it unpleasant and they hide it, just like a cat does.

⁵ An electric dipole consists of two infinitely closed electrical charges of opposite signs and infinite intensity, separated by a dielectric that resists to their attracting force.

⁶ Brazilian Mathematics Education Society.

In Tânia's thesis, there is a passage where one of the groups in the Calculus classroom was hyperactively using the eraser (Baldino & Cabral, 1995). She and I insisted: don't erase it, learn from your mistake. Today I would be more careful in saying that; learning from mistakes is the forbidden rescue. This is the "difficulty" of both the student and the teacher that he is today. In that same group, there was a student who had this "difficulty". In an interview, she collaborated: *Who used to teach me math, she said, was my dad. He had a ruler with an eraser on the end; when I made a mistake, he would hit my hand; it hurt...* In other words, any rescue was *punished*. This discourse of the Other formed that student's unconscious. It became her "difficulty."

A colleague, Alexandre Pais, commented: That's it. The excrement brings a truth to the world. The truth of the subject. The culture (of silence) works tirelessly to hide this truth. Lacan says that culture is like a "shit disposal of society," that is, it provides the necessary decorum for what is repressed. At a certain point, this decorum takes the form of the discreet charm of the bourgeoisie, and silence imposes itself through permanent noise. Like the hysteric lady who never stops talking in order to prevent silence from settling in.

Comment (by Alexandre Pais)

Nowadays, there is no charm at all. If you do not agree, you either shut up, or you're censored, imprisoned, or murdered. No one tries to explain anymore. Ideology does not work. It's just brute force. When someone draws attention to what is happening in Gaza, for example, saying something naive like, "Look, they're bombing children, this is not right!", there are still those who try to justify it ("Oh, these are human shields, it's Hamas's fault"), but most of the time what we see is the imposition of silence through brute force: "Don't make noise, this doesn't concern you, move on!"

Complement

If we accept that the error in mathematics mirrors the process of anal defecation, considering that on this list no one has yet protested, certain consequences are inevitable, and it will not be easy to express them in an academic way.

If the error is a detachment of the subject, referred to the Other, *it's you, but it's not yours*, one cannot avoid concluding that this holds true for the other deliveries of the speaking subject in all representations through signifiers. Therefore, writing and speaking have been rehearsed as defecation at the anal stage; it includes the risk of defecating at the wrong time and the relief of defecating at the required moment. I had a colleague who said she felt "fulfilled" after giving a totally expository class. In other words, short and sweet, that's what the presenter of the *séance magistral* does, especially as pomp and circumstance increase. Lacan could never have said that because, after all... he spoke to so many people, and at the right time...

The same goes for the authors of the rich bourgeois literature and for the speeches at the UN; in short, it applies to us as well. For me, this doesn't concern me; on the contrary, it allows me to understand much; it justifies the motto *one teaches by listening, one learns by speaking*. Holding back the feces until the moment of explosion explains the subject's decision to dare to speak and to submit to the judgment of the other: the meaning is no longer his. Michel Foucault, in the inaugural class, (Foucault, 1971) said he wished that a nameless voice had preceded him so that he could represent himself only by intervening in its silences. On the other hand, in the last pages of Seminar 11, Lacan (1973, XX-2) states that the psychoanalyst himself plays the role of the hypnotized; in other words, he takes on the role of the toilet bowl, collecting what the patient brings him. Not by chance, the translation of this passage is wrong, and even conveys the opposite, both in the

Brazilian and American translations (Lacan, 1964, p. 258; 1978, p. 273). It is a clear symptom of what cannot be said, the Great Silence.

Finally, I pay homage to my colleague who helped me understand the reach of this observation; I do not hide his name: Marco Antonio Wolf. He showed me with his *pobbb...* the bourgeois family, which was my family, in an act of organizing its ideology and accommodating its excrements. Why was it impossible for him to talk about that? “What is foreclosed from within returns from the outside,” says Lacan about the psychotic (Lacan, 1973, VI-3). The dipole is something “primordial,” that does not reach the verbal level to be “repressed.” In fact, if rejected at the pre-verbal level, it remains immune to the action of the signifier. Let us remember that the exclusive certainty exhaustively sought for the foundation of mathematics, as Gödel showed, will also not be found in the realm of the signifier, because self-reference is constitutive of language (Cabral & Baldino, 2024). However, the partial certainties that mathematics provides are undeniable. Here we have the symptom that something is happening at the tension level of the fundamental dipole that characterizes the living being, which in language appears as Moore (2022) suggests: mathematics is the sister of psychosis.

When the opposition present in the fundamental dipole is foreclosed, (*vorwerfen*) the signifier takes on a radical autonomy in relation to the meaning, and psychosis is established. Considering NATO's aggression toward Russia and Zionism's aggression toward the Palestinians, it seems that something similar occurs in geopolitics. The Capital, Marx says, is an *automatisches* Subjekt. Lacan would add: this subject addresses gold as the Other. However, with the end of the gold standard in 1973, its access to the big Other was foreclosed and Capital was free to pursue its only desire which is growing, regardless of human rights and climate change. In 1872, Paul Lafargue, a son-in-law of Marx, wrote a parody in the style of my Neuron-z (Baldino, 2019); in that parody, a character says:

We need religion to curb the masses. But what religion? It must be a new religion. Now, then, the only religion that answers the requirements of our days is the Religion of Capital. Capital is the true, only and omnipotent God. (Lafargue, 1872)

Today I would add to this parody that God has developed the ability to fulminate anyone almost anywhere in the world. God became psychotic and leads a fascist tide that brings the planetary destruction from the horizon to the decision table. Capital is the psychosis of God.

Early Affective Factors of Cognition

This is a theoretical section based on two reports of real classroom episodes. It focuses on the subjective formation under the demand of the Other. The supporting theory is that exposed in Lacan's *Seminar X: Anxiety*. The episodes refer to the application of Pythagoras' theorem in freshman calculus. The earliness of cognitive affective factors is the first time the subject encounters the big Other represented by the mother at the entrance of the realm of signifiers, which occurs at the exit of the anal stage. We show how the *affects that remain drifting around the primary scenes of the anal stage will be recognized later as cognitive factors* by the adult subject in the learning situations of the school credit system.

On “Mathematics”

I would not dare to deal with such a topic while relying only on a vague commonsense notion of what people call “mathematics”. In Cabral and Baldino (2022) we argued that due to very singular social circumstances, in Ancient Greece, by the time of Pythagoras, there emerged a special kind of discourse that tried to avoid the sliding of the signified under the significant. We

call it quilted speech. According to our development there, from a dialectical process along history resulted, on one hand, this very particular form of speech and, on the other, a community of speech integrated into what Lacan calls the big Other, organized around the task of watching over the statute of the last historical form of quilted speech, which we call *M20*, mathematics of the twentieth century. This community decides what is right and what is wrong, which statements are valid and which do not make sense. We call it Mathematics, with a capital M and no quotation marks. It is from the result of a historical process, that is, as subjects of Mathematics, that we may refer to the members of this community as the mathematicians. Since we are focusing on early affective cognition factors, we should consider the entrance of the subject in the realm of signifiers that occurs under the demand of the mother at the exit of the anal stage.

The anal level is the first time that the subject has occasion to recognize himself in something, in an object around which revolves this demand of the mother: 'Hold on to it; give it up'. 'And if I give it up, where does it go?' I do not need to remind you of the importance of these two phases, [retain and release]. This little pile of shit is obtained on demand [like the analytical literature], it is admired: 'what lovely caca!' But this demand also implies, at the same time, that it should be disavowed, because the subject is taught all the same, that he must not have too many relationships with this lovely caca. (Lacan, 1962–63, 19.6.63, ch. XXIII-8)

If the subject insists in considering this object as the semblant of *a*, he will raise from the other a *don't* in a tone that makes it clear that under this signifier, there is no possibility of sliding of any signified. *For the first time the subject will have faced a quilted speech.* He may repress this signifier *don't* when later he looks for his desire in the jouissance resulting from the adventures of all sorts of disobediences, away from the sight of the Other. However, the affects raised by the primary scenes of the anal stage will not be repressed, since affects are never repressed (Lacan, 1962–63, 14.11.62, ch. I-10). The affects raised by the *don't*, remain drifting around this scene and become available to be recognized later, when the subject is introduced to the fully quilted speech of arithmetic and stumbles upon the error, a signifier that admits no sliding of the signified under it, and that can be checked by finger counting; hence the determining importance of the two phases of retaining and releasing.

If the signifiers from which emerge the affects of these primary scenes are only repressed, they may be revived by the subject later on, as we show in our Report 2, below. However, if the repression of the *don't* reaches the degree of foreclosure, the whole primary scene is erased as if it had never happened. In this case, quilted speeches will remain forever out of the subject's reach, and the only strategy that he will have to face the demand of the school credit system will be the psychotic strategy of rote learning for the test.

Why Pythagoras?

It is not by chance that the two reports sustaining this article refer to the application of the theorem of Pythagoras in calculus courses. The reports were imposed by the force of classroom episodes. This force stems from the fact that *the affects raised today as cognition factors by this theorem are unavoidably traced back to the anal stage.* In the theorem, three asunder parts of a right triangle are held together into a single unit by a quilted speech assuring that the values attributed to two of these parts determines the value of the third one. In the anal stage, also three asunder signifiers are held together by the demand of the mother, whose *don't* is a proto quilted speech. It is from you but it is not for you. These three signifiers are the excrement as ceded *agalma*, as object *a* and as unpleasant object. The precarious unit thereby obtained by the unifying demand of the mother is called the Ego, a unit bestowed upon the subject by the big Other. *The affects drifting around the*

assemblage of the Ego will emerge in each application of the theorem of Pythagoras as cognitive affective factors, hence the so-called difficulties with this theorem. Thales' theorem is subjected to the same collection of different parts under a unit, but the quilting, called proportions, is easier to deal with, than the square root of Pythagoras' theorem.

We have there a certain relationship of the constitution of the subject, as divided, as ambivalent in relation to a demand of the Other. We do not see why all of this, for example, should not pass completely into the background, should not be swept away with the introduction of something which is supposed to be henceforth completely external, foreign, the relationship of desire and specifically that of sexual desire. (Lacan, 1962–63, 19.6.63, ch. XXIII-9)

However, we must not forget that our freshman students are just entering the domain of sexual desire. For them, this page has not yet been turned, hence the proverbial difficulties with calculus.

Report 1: An Incursion into the Big Other

It is an afternoon of December 1987. I am in a room of the Federal University of Rio de Janeiro together with some ten students who came to check the grades for their midterm tests in Calculus I for the Pharmacology program. Among the students, José Airton (JA) diligently worked during the semester, always trying to learn, promptly raising his hand when he did not understand, and praising our Solidarity Assimilation Methodology, which we introduced at CERME12. Nevertheless, he still has not passed and will have to take the final exam. He receives his paper, makes no remarks about the 35% grade and starts asking questions to determine where he made mistakes. The group gathers around his seat; I am standing behind him. The midterm question reads: Trim off the circle of the left-hand-side figure and wrap it up to form a cone as in the right-hand-side figure. It is known that $OB = OC = 5$ cm. Calculate the volume of the cone for the values of the radius $r = 4$ cm, 3 cm and 2 cm. Express the volume as a function of the radius.

Figure 1. The midterm exam question.

JA had correctly matched the values of b for $r = 2$ and $r = 3$, but his values for $r = 4$ and $r = 1$ did not match. This last one had not been asked for. Next, applying the formula for the volume, he had found b as a function of V and r and had replaced b with this value into the formula for the volume, without realizing that he had arrived at a trivial equality:

$$h = \frac{3V}{\pi r^2} \rightarrow V = \frac{1}{3} \pi r^2 \frac{3V}{\pi r^2}.$$

Look, the question asked for V as a function of r , I say. In your formula you have V as a function of V . He admits the error, but wants to locate it precisely. Actually, you have almost solved the question, I say, indicating the table that he had produced with the values of r and h . Here you already have h as a function of r . It is just a matter of writing it down.

He seems to have not understood. I insist: What calculation have you done to arrive at this result $h = 3.5$ when $r = 4$? He takes half a minute and finally writes $h^2 + r^2 = 5^2$, $h^2 + 16 = 25$. He explains: To get at 25, h^2 must be 9, hence, h must be 3. He does the operations without writing them, completing the gap and extracting the square root.

- How did you get 3.5 here in the table?

- Yes, I made a mistake. OK, it is an error of arithmetic. But how did you find 4.5 here, when $r = 2$?

He manipulates the calculator and says it is 4.58. What calculation did you do? I calculated square root of 21. He only recognizes the results of the calculator as something that he had done.

- Yes, but before that, what calculation did you do?

- No calculation, he answers surprised.

- You started with 2, how did you get 21?

The dialogue is simplified here. It takes twenty minutes of back and forth repetitions, demands for him to repeat what he had said, and encouragement from the surrounding group. After one semester of group work with the class of eighty students, this group is well aware that no positive answers should be given to JA's questions; they know that this would kill his opportunity to learn and they join me in asking questions that would lead him to verbalize what he had done. In our classroom discussions, many times I had insisted that one teaches by listening and learns by talking. Therefore the group acted as a perfect representative of the big Other in whose field JA was searching for his small a object, the cause of his desire to learn.

At this moment I grab the calculator, turn it towards me to hide the keys from him and ask: I have a 2 here on the display, what keys should I press to get 21? Finally, he verbalizes that he had squared the 2. OK, you have squared the 2. And then what? I subtracted 25. But 4 minus 25 is minus 21, I remarked. How did you extract the root of minus 21? This step takes us another ten minutes. Finally, JA realizes that it is from 25 that he must subtract 4, not conversely. Spontaneously he writes down on a blank part of the protocol: $r^2 + h^2 = 25$, $h^2 = 25 - r^2$. He tries to make explicit the value of h . He hesitates for a moment, and writes: $r^2 - 25$. He stops, realizes that this will not work, rejects what he is doing and restarts, now apparently decides to make everything clear to everyone around him. The pitch in his voice changes, he accommodates himself at the edge of his seat, looks for a blank part of the protocol and writes with a firm hand:

$$h = \sqrt{R^2 -}$$

He immediately stops, scratches

$$\sqrt{\cancel{R^2 -}}$$

and writes, while simultaneously resetting the explanation:

$$h = \sqrt{25 - R^2}.$$

I point at the scratched bit and ask what is this? This is nothing, was his prompt answer, while resetting the explanation and deviating from the scratched bit as if it had never had any importance in his life.

In the years that followed, I collected many examples of this sort of *acte raté* and referred to them as the *moment of learning*, which some authors say is impossible to locate. In the next report, the *acte raté* became dramatic, perhaps even dangerous. How far back had JA to go so that the affects drifting around the nonsensical signifier to which he was stubbornly attached would find resonances with the signifiers of a past scene? He recognized his undue preference for R^2 , the so-called independent variable of the problem to start making explicit the value of h ; he called it up to be nullified and reversed his strategy, but nowhere did he indicate to be using a quilted speech to deal with the theorem. The next time the theorem appears, he will be more flexible in his affective attachments and will be more ready to speak his thoughts out.

Report 2: An Example of Regression

It is a morning of April 2005, we are in room 5 of UERGS⁷, Guaíba campus. It is the third consecutive semester that I teach Calculus I to Computer Engineering, so I have students who failed in the two previous semesters and are taking the course for the third time. Among them, there is a group comprised of Jo and two classmates. In the first class I had insisted they should break apart and integrate themselves into other groups, since they had already worked together unsuccessfully for two semesters, but they insisted on remaining together. Once more, I emphasized the exercises whose solutions depend on the theorems of Thales and Pythagoras, and whose statements are “write such magnitude as a function of this one”. The exams were open book, with questions whose statements were slightly different from those worked in class and in office hours, assigned upon request. Jo, and his two classmates, have a historic difficulty in applying the Pythagoras theorem. The two friends usually waited for Jo to tell them what to do.

In this class, Jo's group started working out an exercise up to the point where the theorem of Pythagoras should be evoked. I watch them from the back of the room. They stop; a certain uneasiness seems to have been installed in the group. Jo looks at me as if he is going to call for my help as they usually did. I walk casually in the room and, passing by the group, I say: it is up to you, and return to my silent position as an observer. I was thinking about Lacan's four speeches, the silent signifier S_1 in the position of demand raises the hysterics; they must assume the responsibility for remaining together, we cannot go through all that again. At a certain moment Jo shouts: Hell, it's Pythagoras!! He stresses his sentence with such an energetic gesture that the pen flies from his hand. I pick it up and hand it to the group without saying a word. Jo then finishes the exercise and explains the solution to his peers, instead of waiting for them to ask him what to do, as usual. From this day on, Jo changed his attitude with respect to the course. He explicitly took leadership of the group. My temporary contract expired and another teacher came to replace me and finish the course. Jo passed, his peers didn't. Jo then passed the course of differential equations and Laplace transforms under another teacher and was my student again in 2006; he passed Fourier transforms and finally graduated. In the next year we learned that he was in Germany for his MS and eventually for his Doctorate, sponsored by a fellowship of the German government. Sometime later he came to campus for a short visit. I invited him to talk to my students about his work. We remembered the 2005 episode, as a pertinent example to the students.

⁷ State University of Rio Grande do Sul, Guaíba campus.

Later that day, in a casual conversation with Tânia and I, Jo confided: When I received the news of my second failure in Calculus, he said, I went home, laid my head on my mother's lap and cried. This is one case where we do not have to look for it, and reality speaks for itself: the affective affinity with the primitive scenes of the anal stage could not be more explicit.

When Jo was about to graduate, a new episode struck in me a flash of fear. The students came hurriedly to tell me that Jo had had a motorcycle accident at the entrance of campus and was in the nearby municipal health service. I hurried to get there. He was conscious, and just a little confused about what had happened. He had not been hit; a car had invaded his lane and hit the car in front of him. He tried to swerve and went off the road into a ditch. He phoned his mother and asked me to appease her. Later, remembering the episode, I asked myself: should he have tried to swerve? Or was this an *acte raté*? The words of Jorge Forbes of many years ago came to my mind, when we told him that we were reading Lacan to understand our classroom practice: "Beware. You are dealing with a highly dangerous virus," he said.

Comment on the Two Reports

I hope to have provided some support for A. Ghosh's statement that "Modulation of affective responses remains a significant aspect of 21st century mathematics education" (Ghosh, 2021, p. 164). I hope to have shown that, for such a modulation to become effective, it must start at the anal stage, with instructions to parents. For instance, it seems evident that JA's mother did not usually ask him to talk about what he had done after he defecated. Perhaps we may conjecture the opposite, that such conversations were not welcome. Jo's mother, on the other hand, by offering her lap to her already adult son, encouraged him to identify his present cognitive affects in the ágalma of her breast, resetting the role of her unifying demand in the formation of her son's Ego... and it worked!

Closure, Mathematics and Psychosis

I will rely on the mathema (Figure 2) presented by Lacan (1981, I-3) to elicit the relation of mathematics and psychosis suggested in Moore (2022).

Figure 2. Two mathema from Lacan's seminar on psychoses.

Normally, when we prepare a lecture or prepare ourselves for a class or exam, we (S) talk to ourselves, (ego), about our narcissistic image (a') in the left-side matheme. We make this image to be a function of our past incursions in the field of the other in search of our desire. The subject talks to the Other about his ego in terms of quilted speeches.

However, if the repression of the signifier *don't* in the initial contact of the subject with quilted speeches reaches the degree of forclusion (*Verwerfung*) the whole primary scene is erased as if it had never happened. In this case, quilted speeches will remain forever out of the subject's reach, and the only strategy that she will have to face the demand of the school credit system will be the

psychotic strategy of rote learning for the test. The subject allies with her ego and both go looking together for the best way to cope with exams, refining the initial rote learning to incredibly high levels to give us the feeling that she is using a legitimate mathematics reasoning, an *identity-quilted speech* of Cabral and Baldino (2024). The student is not cheating! She is really doing her best to cope with something that “the teacher holds as very important but that she cannot find out what it is”.⁸

Whatever comes from the Other, such as criticism or intended help, is absorbed directly by the imaginary circuit $a-a'$ as signs alerting that the narcissistic image should be improved. This arrangement is a precarious solution for the subject. A stressing situation may reverse the imaginary circuit and the narcissistic image starts talking by itself to the subject; hence the hallucination as in the emblematic situation below (see Figure 3).

Mathematics teaching is universally constrained by the credit system. The students' desire is focused on passing and getting the certificate. The teacher is constrained to a syllabus, to a limited time and to supervision vigilance. Under these constraints the teacher is obliged to launch the student into the path of a logic exterior to that of the signifier and teach for the test, stimulating the student to behave as the psychotic. “Behind all the life conquered by the body, lies forever a dead soul”.⁹ Soul's murder, Schreber used to say. The credit system turns mathematics into psychosis.

I could report a case where mathematics triggered true psychosis; it is the case of a humble man who spent the whole monthly home budget buying a very advanced mathematics book and assured: “I see these function functioning”. Fortunately, his wife managed to have the book turned back. In resume, the credit system produces psychosis out of mathematics. Here his an emblematic example of hallucination in mathematics (see Figure 3).

b) $\int \frac{5+3x^2}{\sqrt{15x+3x^3}} dx = \int \frac{5+3x^2}{\sqrt{u}} \cdot \frac{du}{15+9x^2}$

$u = 15x + 3x^3$
 $du = (15 + 9x^2) \cdot dx$
 $dx = \frac{du}{15 + 9x^2}$

$\int \frac{(5+3x^2) \cdot du}{\sqrt{u} \cdot (15+9x^2)} = \int \frac{5+3x^2}{15+9x^2} \cdot \frac{du}{\sqrt{u}}$

$\int \left(\frac{5+3x^2}{15+9x^2} \right) \cdot \frac{du}{\sqrt{u}} = \frac{2}{3} \int \frac{1}{\sqrt{u}} \cdot du = \frac{2}{3} \sqrt{u}$

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Figure 3. An example of hallucination in mathematics.

The student correctly develops the antidifferentiation process and substitutes dx back into the integral. Then he carries out the following simplification, simultaneously violating the equality sign.

$$\frac{5+3x^2}{15+9x^2} \rightarrow \frac{5+3}{15+9} \rightarrow \frac{5}{15} + \frac{3}{9} \rightarrow \frac{1}{3} + \frac{1}{3} = \frac{2}{3}$$

The signifiers start associating by themselves.

⁸ Testimony of a graduate Student.

⁹ Poem of Lys da Cunha Reis, pseudonym of Luiza R. Baldino.

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